

Fig. 1: Standard of chromatogram curve for the antibiotic Amoxicillin by HPLC.

Fig. 2: Standard of chromatogram curve for the antibiotic Ciprofloxacin by HPLC.

Fig. 3: Standard of chromatogram curve of the antibiotic Levofloxacin by HPLC.

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (Mau)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.277	108.385	13.949	35.6	32.0	Amoxicillin

Fig.4: Chromotogram of the antibiotic Amoxicillin in water (Autumn) in the first station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.277	343.890	27.359	76.2	60.3	Amoxicillin

Fig. 5: Chromotogram of the antibiotic Amoxicillin in water (Autumn) in the second station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
2	7.287	51.324	5.352	10.0	8.1	Ciprofloxacin
3	8.530	201.871	20.464	39.3	30.9	Levofloxacin

Fig. 6: chromatogram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in water (Autumn) at the first station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
2	7.287	47.925	4.967	8.6	6.7	Ciprofloxacin
3	8.530	166.525	16.130	29.9	21.7	Levofloxacin

Fig. 7: chromatogram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in water (Autumn) at the second station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.280	171.488	31.356	83.0	84.7	Amoxicillin

Fig. 8: Chromotogram of the antibiotic Amoxicillin in water (winter) in the first station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.280	134.210	16.410	49.7	44.4	Amoxicillin

Fig. 9: Chromotogram of the antibiotic Amoxicillin in water (winter) in the second station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
4	7.287	116.622	8.892	10.8	4.6	Ciprofloxacin
5	8.527	241.103	20.123	22.3	10.4	Levofloxacin

Fig. 10: chromatogram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in water (winter) in the first station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
3	7.287	195.435	13.578	15.4	6.6	Ciprofloxacin
4	8.527	251.901	21.120	19.8	10.3	Levofloxacin

Fig. 11: chromatogram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in water (winter) in the second station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.273	286.402	29.648	38.3	38.6	Amoxicillin

Fig. 12: Chromotogram of the antibiotic Amoxicillin in water (spring) in the first station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.280	233.754	15.828	56.3	37.9	Amoxicillin

Fig. 13: Chromotogram of the antibiotic Amoxicillin in water (spring) in the second station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
4	7.287	283.597	17.197	25.0	10.0	Ciprofloxacin
5	8.527	297.605	23.138	26.3	13.4	Levofloxacin

Fig. 14: chromatogram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in water (spring) at the first station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
4	7.287	258.535	16.171	18.4	9.0	Ciprofloxacin
5	8.527	507.371	31.871	36.1	17.8	Levofloxacin

Fig. 15: chromatogram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in water (spring) at the second station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.280	222.750	22.887	41.6	33.0	Amoxicillin

Fig.16: Chromotogram of the antibiotic Amoxicillin in water (summer) in the first station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.280	267.805	40.729	42.7	44.3	Amoxicillin

Fig. 17: Chromotogram of the antibiotic Amoxicillin in water (summer) in the second station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
4	7.287	186.261	11.851	13.7	6.4	Ciprofloxacin
5	8.530	443.575	33.100	32.6	17.9	Levofloxacin

Fig. 18: chromatogram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in water (summer) in the first station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
4	7.287	89.489	7.458	9.1	3.7	Ciprofloxacin
5	8.527	153.784	14.837	15.6	7.5	Levofloxacin

Fig. 19: chromatogram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in water (summer) in the second station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.273	214.352	23.355	38.3	41.1	Amoxicillin

Fig. 20: Chromotogram of the antibiotic Amoxicillin in sediment (Autumn) in the first station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.273	332.703	32.582	47.6	47.7	Amoxicillin

Fig. 21: Chromotogram of the antibiotic Amoxicillin in sediment (Autumn) at the second station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
4	7.290	87.656	5.530	17.7	13.8	Ciprofloxacin
5	8.527	101.006	6.665	20.4	16.7	Levofloxacin

Fig. 22: chromatogram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in sediment (Autumn) at first station HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
3	7.290	94.012	5.696	17.7	15.1	Ciprofloxacin
4	8.527	179.172	9.578	33.7	25.4	Levofloxacin

Fig. 23: chromatogram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in sediment (Autumn) at the second station HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.280	740.759	50.125	49.7	41.6	Amoxicillin

Fig. 24: Chromotogram of the antibiotic Amoxicillin in sediment (winter) in the first station by HPLC device

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.280	152.293	16.360	16.9	19.2	Amoxicillin

Fig. 25: Chromotogram of the antibiotic Amoxicillin in sediment (winter) at the second station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
2	7.287	29.411	4.091	1.9	2.3	Ciprofloxacin
3	8.527	56.490	7.561	3.6	4.2	Levofloxacin

Fig. 26: chromatogram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in the (winter) sediment of the first station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
2	7.287	21.978	3.243	5.0	2.9	Ciprofloxacin
3	8.527	102.914	12.013	23.4	10.9	Levofloxacin

Fig. 27: chromatogram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in sediment (winter) in the second station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.280	53.317	6.557	12.9	12.7	Amoxicillin

Fig. 28: Chromotogram of the antibiotic Amoxicillin in sediment (spring) in the first station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.280	150.343	17.915	29.9	28.6	Amoxicillin

Fig. 29: Chromotogram of the antibiotic Amoxicillin in sediment (spring) at the second station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
2	7.287	76.854	7.688	10.8	5.9	Ciprofloxacin
3	8.527	121.284	11.471	17.0	8.9	Levofloxacin

Fig. 30: chromatogram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in the sediment (spring) of the first station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
4	7.287	80.267	7.785	8.3	4.2	Ciprofloxacin
5	8.527	136.034	13.417	14.1	7.2	Levofloxacin

Fig. 31: chromatogram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in the sediment (spring) of the second station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.280	106.688	14.460	27.9	27.6	Amoxicillin

Fig. 32: Chromotogram of the antibiotic Amoxicillin in the sediment (summer) in the first station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.280	160.147	18.375	35.8	30.3	Amoxicillin

Fig. 33: Chromotogram of the antibiotic Amoxicillin in the sediment (summer) in the second station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
4	7.287	156.113	10.682	28.7	13.0	Ciprofloxacin
5	8.530	141.617	15.375	26.0	18.7	Levofloxacin

Fig. 34: chromatogram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in sediment (summer) at first station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
3	7.287	27.555	3.371	3.3	3.1	Ciprofloxacin
4	8.530	294.366	23.815	35.8	21.6	Levofloxacin

Fig. 35: chromatogram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in the sediment (summer) at the second station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.280	1965.532	144.391	78.6	71.9	Amoxicillin

Fig. 36: Amoxicillin antibiotic chromatogram in the muscles of Nile tilapia (Autumn) at first station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.280	653.902	72.498	27.6	34.9	Amoxicillin

Fig. 37: Chromatogram of the antibiotic Amoxicillin in the muscles of Nile tilapia (Autumn) at the second station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
3	7.287	187.495	12.708	7.1	3.9	Ciprofloxacin
4	8.530	304.721	23.529	11.5	7.2	Levofloxacin

Fig. 38: chromatogram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in the muscles of Nile tilapia (Autumn) in the first station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
4	7.287	230.222	13.717	14.4	6.4	Ciprofloxacin
5	8.527	507.371	31.871	31.7	14.8	Levofloxacin

Fig. 39: chromatogram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in the muscles of Nile tilapia (Autumn) in the second station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.280	1311.987	112.959	54.1	58.3	Amoxicillin

Fig. 40: Chromotogram of the antibiotic Amoxicillin in the muscles of the Nile tilapia (winter) at the first station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.280	2375.911	166.413	69.2	66.3	Amoxicillin

Fig. 41: Chromotogram of the antibiotic Amoxicillin in the muscles of Nile tilapia (winter) at the second station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
3	7.287	546.009	23.344	26.8	10.1	Ciprofloxacin
4	8.527	688.455	37.796	33.8	16.3	Levofloxacin

Fig. 42: chromatogram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in the muscles of Nile tilapia (winter) in the first station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
4	7.287	83.465	7.117	7.2	6.0	Ciprofloxacin
5	8.530	330.525	27.769	28.7	23.3	Levofloxacin

Fig. 43: chromatogram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in the muscles of Nile tilapia (winter) in the second station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.277	604.263	40.908	61.2	47.4	Amoxicillin

Fig. 44: chromatogram of the antibiotic Amoxicillin in the muscles of Nile tilapia (spring) at the first station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.277	202.271	20.847	28.8	27.9	Amoxicillin

Fig. 45: chromatogram of the antibiotic Amoxicillin in the muscles of Nile tilapia (spring) at the second station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
3	7.287	220.311	14.677	19.0	7.7	Ciprofloxacin
4	8.527	279.457	22.450	24.1	11.8	Levofloxacin

Fig. 46: chromatogram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in the muscles of Nile tilapia (spring) in the first station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
4	7.287	310.795	17.635	22.3	8.6	Ciprofloxacin
5	8.527	347.234	24.111	25.0	11.8	Levofloxacin

Fig. 47: chromatogram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in the muscle of Nile tilapia (spring) in the second station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.280	368.015	50.305	54.9	52.3	Amoxicillin

Fig. 48: Chromotogram of the antibiotic Amoxicillin in the muscles of the Nile tilapia (summer) in the first station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.280	206.116	20.553	35.3	27.3	Amoxicillin

Fig. 49: chromatogram of antibiotic Amoxicillin in muscles of Nile tilapia (summer) at second station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
4	7.287	89.365	8.070	8.8	4.0	Ciprofloxacin
5	8.527	65.001	8.900	6.4	4.4	Levofloxacin

Fig. 50: chromatogram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in the muscles of Nile tilapia (summer) in the first station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
4	7.287	167.882	12.333	16.0	6.9	Ciprofloxacin
5	8.527	374.513	24.741	35.6	13.8	Levofloxacin

Fig. 51: chromatogram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in the muscles of Nile tilapia (summer) in the second station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.280	511.846	63.078	30.1	41.1	Amoxicillin

Fig. 52: Chromotogram of the antibiotic Amoxicillin in the liver of Nile tilapia (Autumn) at the first station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.280	188.480	20.155	25.8	26.1	Amoxicillin

Fig. 53: Chromotogram of the antibiotic Amoxicillin in the liver of Nile tilapia (Autumn) at the second station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
4	7.287	124.844	9.381	14.3	6.7	Ciprofloxacin
5	8.527	152.032	15.424	17.4	11.1	Levofloxacin

Fig. 54: chromatogram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in the liver of Nile tilapia (Autumn) at the first station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
4	7.287	69.491	7.142	11.6	6.1	Ciprofloxacin
5	8.527	146.969	14.792	24.5	12.7	Levofloxacin

Fig. 55: chromatogram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in the liver of Nile tilapia (Autumn) in the second station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.280	617.562	70.884	41.7	50.0	Amoxicillin

Fig. 56: Chromotogram of the antibiotic Amoxicillin in the liver of Nile tilapia (winter) at the first station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.280	758.326	81.552	55.3	59.8	Amoxicillin

Fig. 57: Chromotogram of the antibiotic Amoxicillin in the liver of Nile tilapia (winter) at the second station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
4	7.287	321.353	14.598	16.3	8.0	Ciprofloxacin
5	8.530	1022.952	53.184	51.9	29.1	Levofloxacin

Fig. 58: chromatogram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in the liver of Nile tilapia (winter) in the first station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
3	7.287	368.659	18.418	21.3	8.1	Ciprofloxacin
4	8.527	402.486	27.479	23.2	12.1	Levofloxacin

Fig. 59: chromatogram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in the liver of Nile tilapia (winter) in the second station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.280	100.475	13.787	29.2	28.5	Amoxicillin

Fig. 60: Chromotogram of the antibiotic Amoxicillin in the liver of Nile tilapia (spring) at the first station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.280	216.490	22.609	28.8	28.2	Amoxicillin

Fig. 61: Chromotogram of the antibiotic Amoxicillin in the liver of Nile tilapia (spring) at the second station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
3	7.287	69.491	7.142	6.2	3.7	Ciprofloxacin
4	8.527	245.779	20.558	21.8	10.8	Levofloxacin

Fig. 62: Chromotram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in the liver of Nile tilapia (spring) in the first station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
3	7.287	163.436	12.376	19.4	9.5	Ciprofloxacin
4	8.527	268.147	21.499	31.9	16.5	Levofloxacin

Fig. 63: chromatogram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in the liver of Nile tilapia (spring) in the second station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.280	367.323	42.953	56.2	52.6	Amoxicillin

Fig. 64: Chromotogram of the antibiotic Amoxicillin in the liver of Nile tilapia (summer) at the first station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
1	4.280	269.969	25.114	26.8	24.7	Amoxicillin

Fig. 65: Chromotogram of the antibiotic Amoxicillin in the liver of Nile tilapia (summer) at the second station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
4	7.287	30.291	4.177	3.0	2.1	Ciprofloxacin
5	8.527	62.484	8.123	6.2	4.2	Levofloxacin

Fig. 66: chromatogram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in the liver of Nile tilapia (summer) in the first station by HPLC

Peak	Reten Time(min)	Area (mAU.s)	Height (mAU)	Area (%)	Height (%)	Compound Name
3	7.287	52.937	5.111	7.4	5.1	Ciprofloxacin
4	8.530	228.472	22.429	31.9	22.4	Levofloxacin

Fig. 67: chromatogram of the antibiotics Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin in the liver of Nile tilapia (summer) in the second station by HPLC